

EMP-APAC

Energy Transformation in Malaysia: Sustainable Pathways for the Energy Sector

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ABOUT EMP-APAC

The Energy Modelling Platform for Asia and the Pacific (EMP-APAC) is a prominent initiative organized by the Climate Compatible Growth community, offering participants access to expert trainers, interactive discussion forums, and personalized coaching in utilizing models and tools for energy planning and analysis. This free program emphasizes inclusivity and collaboration within the energy sector, providing a platform for professionals and academics to enhance their skills in energy modelling.

Notably, all the models and tools presented are both free and open source, ensuring accessibility for a wide range of participants. Participants benefit not only from the event itself but also gain the flexibility to engage with courses at their own pace, thanks to the availability of resources on the OpenLearn platform.

In addition to the structured training sessions, EMP-APAC fosters a community dedicated to sustainable energy practices in the region. The platform encourages knowledge exchange and collaboration among participants, supporting the development of low-carbon, resilient, and sustainable energy systems across Asia and the Pacific.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Malaysia's electricity sector is heavily reliant on fossil fuels, which account for 80% of generation, leaving renewable energy at just 20%, far below the global average. This dependence poses risks to decarbonization and energy security, particularly as electricity demand grows with economic development. The National Energy Transition Roadmap sets ambitious targets to achieve 40% renewable energy by 2035 and 70% by 2050, with solar energy expected to play a bigger contribution to installed capacity of renewable energy.

This study evaluates three scenarios using the OSeMOSYS model: Business-As-Usual (BAU), Renewable Energy Scenario (RES), and Carbon Tax Scenario (CTS). Under BAU, fossil fuels dominate the generation, and emissions will rise 92% by 2050. RES achieves a 55% in electricity generation mix by 2050 and phases out coal by 2040. It is supported by transport electrification, but the power sector remains a major emitter. CTS offers the most cost-effective pathway, combining a carbon tax with CCS deployment in power and industry sectors, reducing emissions by 64.6% relative to BAU. The residual emissions are expected to offset via land use, land-use change and forestry.

Decarbonization requires a multi-sector strategy, balancing renewable expansion, electrification, and CCS in the power and industry sectors, alongside complementary measures such as land use, land-use change and forestry. Prioritizing industrial and power sector mitigation in the near term allows Malaysia to meet climate goals while maintaining energy security and cost efficiency. Future research should focus on improving data accuracy, evaluating emerging technologies, and assessing renewable variability to support robust, evidence-based policy decisions.

INTRODUCTION

Malaysia's electricity sector is heavily dependent on fossil fuels, which account for approximately 80% of total generation, while renewable and low-carbon sources make up only 20%, far below the global renewable average of 41% (Graham *et al.*, 2025). This reliance on fossil fuels presents significant challenges for meeting the nation's decarbonization goals and ensuring long-term energy security, particularly as electricity demand is projected to grow alongside economic development and urbanization.

To address these challenges, Malaysia has outlined a clear pathway for energy transition through the National Energy Transition Roadmap (NETR). The roadmap sets ambitious targets, aiming to increase installed renewable energy capacity to 40% by 2035 and ultimately achieve 70% by 2050 (MEA, 2021). Among all renewable options, solar energy is expected to play a central role due to the country's abundant solar resources as presented in Malaysia Renewable Energy Roadmap (MyRER). This is due to declining technology costs, and flexible deployment opportunities such as rooftop and floating solar systems (SEDA, 2021). Other renewable sources, including geothermal, biomass, and wind, are limited by geographic, technical, and infrastructural constraints, reinforcing the importance of solar in Malaysia's decarbonization strategy.

Given these conditions, this report seeks to examine the evolution of Malaysia's energy sector under the NETR targets. The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. How can Malaysia's power sector evolve to achieve the national target of a 70% installed capacity for renewable energy by 2050?
2. What is the potential impact of implementing a progressive carbon tax and emissions limit on the transformation of Malaysia's energy sector?

Through this analysis, the report aims to assess the opportunities, obstacles, and strategic pathways for achieving a sustainable and low-carbon energy sector in Malaysia.

METHODOLOGY

This study analyses Malaysia's energy sector using a structured modelling approach that comprising of three main steps: data collection, model calibration, and scenario analysis.

Data Collection: Data for 2021–2023 were compiled from the National Energy Balance report (Energy Commission, 2025), NETR (MEA, 2021), MyRER (SEDA, 2021), and other official sources. Information collected includes installed capacities, historical generation by technology, sectoral energy demand (electricity, heat, cooking), and technical parameters of power plants.

Model Calibration: The model was calibrated using historical data to ensure that it accurately represents Malaysia's energy sector. Key assumptions include:

- Annual growth for primary sources extraction such as crude oil, natural gas, biomass are limited to 2%.
- Maximum technical potential for renewable energy plants remains constant through 2021–2050.
- Solar generation is assumed to be 90% utility-scale and 10% off-grid.
- Industrial heating is divided into 40% low-heat demand and 60% high-heat demand.
- Overall energy demand across all sectors grows at 3% annually.

Modelling Approach: The analysis was performed using Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS), a bottom-up linear programming model that identifies the least-cost energy-technology mix to meet projected demand while respecting technical constraints and policy targets (Howells *et al.*, 2011). The Starter Data Kit was adapted to the Malaysian context by updating installed capacities, generation data, and sectoral energy consumption.

The OSeMOSYS was used to model Malaysia's energy transition under three scenarios with each reflecting different policy and technology pathways. These include the Business-As-Usual (BAU), Renewable Energy (RES) and the Carbon Tax (CTS) scenario. **Figure 1** summarizes the main features of the scenarios.

- The BAU scenario serves as a baseline, exploring the non-policy trajectory for Malaysia's power system. It assumes low penetration of new technologies such as solar, hydro, and biomass with no emission limits. It assumes minimal deployment of new technologies, such as solar, hydro, and biomass, with no emission constraints. Energy generation and consumption follow historical patterns, providing a baseline for evaluating the impact of more ambitious transition strategies.
- The RES scenario models an accelerated energy transition, targeting 70% renewable penetration in the installed capacity of power sector by 2050 and a complete phase-out of coal. It also considers increased electrification in the transport sector, with adoption targets for motorcycles and passenger cars only set at 20% by 2030, 50% by 2040, and 80% by 2050. This scenario evaluates the technical and operational implications of a solar-dominated power system.
- The CTS scenario examines the effect of implementing progressive carbon tax on different energy sectors to support Malaysia's decarbonization goals. Similar target with RES scenario where coal is fully phased out by 2050. Under this scenario, CO₂ emissions reduction targets for the energy sector are limited to 4% by 2030, 26% by 2040, and 32% by 2050, relative to 2019 levels (MEA, 2021).

Figure 1: Summary of scenarios explored in the modelling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 illustrates projected electricity generation in Malaysia under three scenarios: BAU, RES and CTS. Electricity generation in Malaysia is expected to grow across all scenarios, driven by rising GDP and population. In the BAU trajectory, generation increases from 647 PJ in 2021 to 1,400 PJ by 2050. Coal and natural gas remain the main sources, contributing about 49% and 30% of total generation, while renewable energy rises only modestly to around 20%, reflecting limited changes in policy or technology.

Under the RES scenario, generation reaches 1,546 PJ by 2050, the highest among the three scenarios. Total generation is higher in this scenario due to increased electricity demand from the electrification of the transport sector. In this scenario, the rapid expansion of renewable energy, primarily from solar and hydro, allows coal to be fully phased out by 2040, with renewables eventually making up 54.9% of the generation mix by 2050.

In the CTS scenario, which introduces carbon taxes and emissions limits to encourage cleaner generation, total output reaches 1,431 PJ by 2050. Coal is also fully phased out by 2040, and natural gas is gradually replaced by natural gas combined cycle with carbon capture (NGSCCS). Renewable energy rises to 29.9%, higher than in BAU but lower than in RES. While the carbon tax provides financial incentives for decarbonization, it is not sufficient on its own to achieve the high renewable share seen in RES without additional supportive policies.

Figure 2: Projected Electricity Annual Generation of Malaysia for the year 2021, 2030, 2040 and 2050.

Figure 3 illustrates the projected total installed electricity generation capacity in Malaysia for 2021, 2030, 2040, and 2050 under the BAU, RES, and CTS scenarios. Overall, installed capacity increases substantially across all scenarios to meet the growing electricity demand. In the BAU scenario, capacity grows moderately from 36 GW in 2021 to 59 GW in 2050. The power system remains dominated by conventional technologies such as coal, natural gas, and existing hydro, with limited expansion of solar and other renewables.

Under the RES scenario, total installed capacity reaches 182 GW by 2050, the highest among the three scenarios. This growth is primarily driven by the aggressive deployment of renewable technologies, particularly solar, to achieve the target of 70% renewable penetration by 2050. As a result, fossil fuel capacity declines, with coal power plant fully

phased out by 2040 and natural gas power plant capacity reduced to accommodate large-scale renewable integration. By 2050, renewables account for 77.2% of total capacity, exceeding the target. This higher share is necessary because renewable technologies have lower capacity factors compared to fossil fuel plants, and additional capacity is required to meet the increased electricity demand from the electrification of the transport sector.

In the CTS scenario, total installed capacity reaches 83 GW by 2050, higher than the BAU scenario but significantly lower than RES. Coal power plant is again fully phased out by 2040, while natural gas power plant is gradually replaced by NGSCCS. Due to the high capacity factor and low emissions of this technology, there is less reliance on solar deployment to meet electricity demand.

Across all scenarios, hydropower reaches its maximum potential in both RES and CTS scenarios by 2050 and 2040, respectively. Solar capacity expands significantly under RES and CTS, driven by renewable targets and decarbonization policies. Overall, these pathways illustrate Malaysia’s potential strategies to expand installed capacity while transitioning to a sustainable, low-carbon power system.

Figure 3: Projected total Installed Capacity in Malaysia for the year 2021, 2030, 2040 and 2050.

The projected usage of fossil fuels in Malaysia between 2021 and 2050, as illustrated in **Figure 4**, shows that natural gas will remain the dominant source of energy across all scenarios. In the CTS scenario, natural gas consumption stays high due to its use NGSCSS. Malaysia’s fossil fuel reserves currently stand at approximately 21,774 PJ of crude oil, 79,834 PJ of natural gas, and 6,797 PJ of coal. Crude oil reserves are projected to be depleted by 2040 under all scenarios, after which the country will need to rely entirely on imported petroleum products from refineries. Natural gas reserves are sufficient to meet domestic demand until around 2050. While coal reserves are adequate

to support domestic consumption, Malaysia will continue to import the majority of its coal due to limited domestic production capacity relative to national demand.

The availability of these reserves directly influences future consumption patterns. Under the BAU pathway, total fossil fuel consumption is projected to rise sharply, reaching 7,048 PJ by 2050, compared to 6,060 PJ under CTS and 4,675 PJ under RES. The RES pathway demonstrates the most significant reduction in fossil fuel use, driven primarily by the substitution of gasoline with electricity in the transport sector and by the expansion of renewable energy capacity. Coal, which accounts for 26.4% of fossil fuel use under BAU, declines drastically to 1.4% under RES and 1.1% under CTS. Liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), the main fuel used for cooking in the residential sector, remains at 3.5% of total consumption under BAU but is fully phased out by 2040 under both RES and CTS. Jet fuel, however, remains constant across all scenarios as it continues to be the only viable option for aviation, given the current economic challenges of adopting sustainable aviation fuels.

Figure 4: Projected usage of fossil fuels in Malaysia for the year 2021, 2030, 2040 and 2050.

Figure 5 presents the projected fuel demand (in PJ) for the transport sector under three scenarios from 2021 to 2050. The optimized potential fuel types in Malaysia include jet fuel, diesel, gasoline, electricity, and hydrogen. In 2021, fuel demand is predominantly met by fossil fuels, totalling 830 PJ. By 2030, overall demand rises slightly, with the BAU scenario reaching 984 PJ. The CTS scenario exhibits a similar demand pattern, as decarbonization measures have not yet been implemented in the transport sector. In contrast, under the RES scenario, demand decreases to 904 PJ. This reduction is attributed to the electrification of passenger cars and motorcycles, which are more energy-efficient than fossil-fuel-powered vehicles. In other words, the fuel consumption per passenger-kilometer is lower.

Projections for 2040 show a more pronounced divergence among the scenarios. Fuel demand under the BAU scenario reaches 1,323 PJ, while RES and CTS scenarios are projected at 1,024 PJ and 1,290 PJ, respectively, reflecting a gradual shift toward alternative fuels, particularly electricity. By 2050, demand under BAU peaks at 1,778 PJ, whereas the RES and CTS scenarios exhibit moderated growth, reaching 1,092 PJ and 1,495 PJ, respectively. Notably, in addition to electricity, hydrogen emerges as a feasible fuel option in 2050 under both the RES and CTS scenarios. Overall, these projections highlight the significant impact of decarbonization strategies and electrification on future fuel demand in Malaysia’s transport sector.

Figure 5: Projected Fuel Demand for Transport Sector in Malaysia for the year 2021, 2030, 2040 and 2050.

The projected CO₂ emissions for Malaysia from 2021 to 2050, presented in **Figure 6**, highlight significant differences between policy scenarios. Under BAU, emissions rise steadily to nearly 494 Mt-CO₂ by 2050. By contrast, RES stabilizes emissions before achieving a moderate decline to 276 Mt-CO₂, representing a 44.1% reduction compared to BAU. The most ambitious pathway, CTS, achieves the largest reduction, lowering emissions to 175 Mt-CO₂ by 2050 which is equivalent to a 64.6% cut. In both RES and CTS, the power and transport sectors are the largest contributors to reductions, together accounting for nearly half of total avoided emissions. The sectoral breakdown shows that under BAU and RES, the power sector dominates emissions, followed by transport and industry. Under CTS, however, transport becomes the largest contributor, followed by “others” and power. The “other” sector refers to the non-energy sectors, specifically the use of energy products for purposes other than fuel for heat or power generation. In this context, it includes all sectors except power, residential, commercial and public services, industry, agriculture, and transport. Notably, the industry sector records negative emissions (-3.82 Mt-CO₂) under CTS due to the adoption of biomass furnaces with CCS for high-heat industrial demand. Furthermore, the remaining 175 Mt-CO₂ under CTS is expected to be offset by land use, land-use change, and forestry to achieve net-zero

emissions. These results make clear that without intervention, emissions will escalate; however, with strong policy measures, substantial reductions are possible. Even so, achieving net-zero will require significant reliance on land use, land-use change, and forestry as a complementary mitigation strategy.

Figure 6: Projected CO₂ Emissions and the contribution of each sector for different Scenario Analysis

The total cost analysis for Malaysia under different policy scenarios, shown in **Figure 7**, indicates that while all pathways involve considerable expenditure, CTS emerges as the most cost-effective option in the long term. By 2050, BAU results in total costs of USD 645 billion, while RES is slightly higher at USD 658 billion due to the substantial capital and operational expenses linked to transport electrification. In comparison, CTS requires USD 625 billion, making it the lowest-cost pathway despite the additional investment in CCS, which proves to be more economical in terms of cost per ton of CO₂ removed. It should be noted that this amount represents the total investment required across the nation for decarbonization, irrespective of whether the funding comes from the government, industry, or consumers. When measured against Malaysia's 2024 GDP of USD 420 billion, the total cost burden under BAU and RES is projected at 1.54 times and 1.56 times GDP, respectively, whereas CTS reduces this burden to 1.48 times GDP. Assuming the investment begins in 2025, it is projected to span 25 years, with annual requirements estimated at approximately 5.9% to 6.2% of the nation's GDP. BAU also faces increasing cost pressures from coal imports as the domestic production is not sufficient to meet the demand, further weakening its viability. These findings suggest that while both RES and CTS pathways significantly reduce emissions, CTS provides a more financially sustainable strategy for Malaysia, balancing environmental goals with economic efficiency. However, the CTS case assumes that fossil fuel imports will remain unconstrained; if external supply limitations occur, this pathway may face additional challenges.

Figure 7: Total Cost Required for Different Scenario Analysis

POLICY INSIGHT

The BAU pathway highlights the risks of inaction. With coal production is insufficient to meet the national demand, Malaysia would be forced to rely on costly imports. Continued dependence on coal would not only expose the country to volatile import prices but also increase overall energy generation costs. Furthermore, emissions under BAU are expected to rise by 92% compared to 2019, placing the country far from meeting its climate commitments.

In the RES, large-scale electrification of the transport sector contributes significantly to emissions reduction. However, electrification alone is insufficient to achieve net-zero by 2050. Even with aggressive renewable capacity expansion, the power sector remains the largest source of emissions, demonstrating that renewables must be complemented by other strategies, such as CCS and other negative emissions technologies, to achieve full decarbonization.

The CTS provides the most cost-effective pathway for deep decarbonization. Analysis shows that deep decarbonization of the power sector is achievable, but only with widespread deployment of CCS. It also indicates that decarbonizing the industrial sector through technologies such as biomass with CCS is more cost-effective (in \$/t-CO₂) than massive electrification of the transport sector. This highlights the need to prioritize industry and power decarbonization in the near term, while continuing to support innovation in transport fuels to reduce long-term reliance on fossil-based jet fuel and heavy-duty transport.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, the analysis demonstrates that decarbonization cannot be achieved by focusing on a single sector. Instead, it requires a coordinated effort across power, transport, and industry to achieve emissions reductions at the lowest possible cost. While renewable energy expansion and transport electrification are critical, they must be complemented by CCS technologies in the power and industry sectors, alongside land use, land-use change, and forestry measures to offset residual emissions. A balanced portfolio approach ensures both cost efficiency and emissions reduction effectiveness, positioning Malaysia to meet its long-term climate goals without compromising energy security.

Future research should focus on improving the accuracy of data inputs to better reflect Malaysia's sectoral realities. This includes refining industrial sector data to differentiate between low- and high-heat demand applications, as well as enhancing transport sector data to capture mode-specific fuel use more precisely. Incorporating emerging technologies with low technology readiness levels, such as hydrogen and advanced biofuels, will also be critical to assessing their potential role in long-term decarbonization. Additionally, uncertainty analysis should be conducted, as renewable energy capacity factors are highly dependent on climate conditions. These steps will provide more robust insights for policymakers and ensure that transition pathways remain aligned with evolving technological and economic conditions.

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